

Peculiarities in the language's use of terminology and professions

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Annotation

This article is about the issue of the methodology of linguistic research and use of terminology and professional terms in the language. The most conceptually important issue not only in Uzbek linguistics, but also in foreign linguistics. Systematic linguistics, which follows the principle of "from specifics to generalities" formed at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, works on the basis of direct observation of specifics and differences, compares them with each other, and aims to reveal common aspects. Systematic study of language was a great achievement of 20th century linguistics. The peculiarity of these studies is that they do not approach linguistic facts autonomously, but pay attention to the discovery of the hidden essence of each linguistic phenomenon. The researcher's attention is more focused on elucidating the relationship between linguistic phenomena.

Key words: terminology, logicians ,primitive weapons ,transmitted, layers, generation.

Introduction

Literary language norms are largely determined by the rich cultural legacy that our ancestors' centuries-old creative activity has left behind. This heritage is shaped by the collection, arrangement, and theoretical and practical application of conventional lexical layers in linguistics. Scholar Sh. Shoabdurahmanov gathered the lexical layers of our language and considered the need for scientific study. He wrote: "It can be said that when the elder generation passes away, the language will remain in their memory if the entire Uzbek traditional lexicon is not recorded in the near future, taking into account all the responsibilities." A portion of the priceless materials that have been saved and brought to us might vanish forever."

The Uzbek language's profession lexicon was initially compiled by renowned

scientist and linguist S. Ibrohimov. In order to create their dictionary, he gathered and linguistically examined a large number of words and terminology associated with vocations that are becoming less common in marriage and have not yet been researched by anybody.

Materials and methods

The vocabulary associated with the profession is distinct from other layers of the language because it is closely linked to the social and cultural evolution of the populace. It has been developed over centuries of labor, proven by experience, and is popular, essential, and traditional.

Social connections terminology have been orally transmitted from one generation to the next as traditions and customs, which have been adopted by succeeding generations. From this vantage point, Names representing areas directly related to people's life and livelihood, that is, food, clothing, housing, and household items, are rich and diverse, and they are considered active lexical layers in terms of use. If we study the objects found in ancient manuscripts and archeological excavations and their names, and compare them with modern concepts, we will get information about the historical development of the Uzbek people.

Delimitation of the concept understood by the word term has become one of the problems facing linguists at the moment. This is due to the wide and sometimes narrow understanding of the term.

Some linguists and logicians include in the term not only the words and expressions related to science and technology, but also the names of all household tools, not only the weapons of the current level of production, but also the names of the primitive weapons of the past, and words related to various professions. For example, when D.K. Zelenin thinks about stable and unstable words in the Vyatsk dialect of the Russian language, he writes about the "term-names" of various weapons and household tools used by Russian peasants at the beginning of the 20th century. Today's Uzbek terminologists also have this tendency. For example, N.M. Murodov, while thinking about terms that are out of date and out of use, used the words *koshchi*, *plough*, which are related to old farming, *parangi*, *chachvan*, *turban*, *kavush*, which are characteristic of the feudal system, as examples of the names of old clothes. brings S. Ibrohimov considers the professional words used by Uzbek artisans from the past periods in the dialects of Fergana to the present, when the industrialization was developed instead of the small handicraft method, partly as a

term, word-term, and more as a lexicon of profession. After him, T.T. Dadakhonova, who studied the lexicon of Chevarism, and who studied the names of dishes. Ikromova also calls professional words words-terms.

Results and discussion

So, when it is understood in a broad sense, first of all, the name of each concrete thing-subject should be called a term. If the term is understood in this way, it would be appropriate to consider the most typical terms to be the adjectives that express a concrete and definite meaning in relation to any concrete cognate noun.

So, it's not just a matter of the term expressing one meaning. In this respect, professional lexicon does not differ from scientific and technical terms.

Terminology, which is separated as a separate group of the vocabulary, is actually a system of words of a scientific (philosophical, social-political, scientific-technical) character with a clear boundary. This system does not consist of a mechanistic set of words, but is a set of words that are semantically interconnected, coordinated with each other, one of which requires the existence of the other, and this feature of them comes from the interconnectedness of scientific or technical structures, weapons, and elements. For example, if there is a cylinder in the internal combustion chamber, it will certainly have a piston and valves that let gas in and out. Therefore, the term cylinder is internally connected with the terms piston and valve, requiring their existence. In this respect, the development of terminology goes along with the development of science and technology. For example, the development of ancient philosophy required the creation of philosophical terms at that time. It is known that these terms later gained great importance in the creation of national terminology in Western European languages.

Thus, the term appeared not only as a specific theme of any concept, but also as a means of expressing its scientific essence, and mainly in written form. When it comes to the lexicon of profession, several important features distinguish it from the term.

Firstly, the terms have a universal meaning depending on the development of science and technology on a global scale, while the words used in the profession have a very narrow meaning, as they belong to a certain local border on the one hand, and to a small profession on the other hand.

Therefore, secondly, there will be dialectal variants of professional lexicon. For example, in Bukhara, Uzbek metalsmiths use a pattern called islimi bargi bodom, but in the Ferghana Valley, it is called almond leaf islimi or almond leaf wrap. Even within a

dialect there are such options. For example, in the field of cast iron (iron casting) in Margilon, the cast part that is tapped into the cart hub is called big mouth, takchoyan, and the cast detail that is tapped on the lip of the cart hub is called chuvchoyan, chuvogizchoyan, small mouth cast iron in various variants. Also compare: bozkum-boskum (ordinary clay used in cast iron), dashkal-choyanbok (slag), internal arrow-drawing nail- small sword (an iron nail as thick as a pencil), bulul-bulol-bilol-burul (iron that sends the air from the furnace to the fire tube), gulsun-gursun-gorzum (a small circle-shaped design element carved in murkana and copper).

Conclusion

It is known that the professional lexicon is included in the social dialects rather than being called specific vocabulary units of territorial dialects. For example, the famous Russian linguist E.D. Polivanov's teacher I.A. Beauduinde based on the teaching of Courtenay about territorial dialects, which are the "horizontal" layer of the language, and social dialects, which are the "vertical" layer of the language. found it necessary to introduce it into the dialects specific to social groups.

From this point of view, social dialects and territorial dialects seem to be opposed to each other. When it comes to the professional lexicon in the Uzbek language, this layer of the vocabulary is, on the one hand, characteristic of social dialects due to its meaning system and nominative function, because it is used only in a certain narrow circle of people. This is its social dialectic aspect.

Secondly, the lexicon of the profession, as shown above, has a certain territorial character. This is characteristic of its territorial dialect.

So, the professional lexicon combines the character of both social and territorial dialect. Therefore, there is truth in the opinion of Academician V. M. Zhirmunsky that "... it can be said that it is wrong to contrast "territorial" and "social" dialects." In essence, the occupational lexicon reflects the social stratification of the territorial dialect. In this respect, it forms a group of territorial dialect vocabulary. Therefore, it would not be appropriate to include scientific terminology in this category, of course.

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